

ISSN: 2181-4562

DOI Journal 10.56017/2181-4562

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PAGES

JOCAA

МАДАНИЈАТ ВА САНЈАТ

Journal of Culture and Art

Volume I, Issue 2

April | 2023

КУЛТУРА И ИСКУССТВО

ISSN: 2181-4562
DOI Journal 10.56017/2181-4562

МАДАНИЯТ ВА САЊАТ ЖУРНАЛИ

I-ЖИЛД, 2-СОҢ

ЖУРНАЛ КУЛЬТУРА И ИСКУССТВО

ТОМ-I, НОМЕР-2

JOURNAL OF CULTURE AND ART

VOLUME-I, ISSUE-2

ТОШКЕНТ – 2023

МАДАНИЯТ ВА САНЪАТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ КУЛЬТУРА И ИСКУССТВА | JOURNAL OF CULTURE AND ART

№ 2 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.56017/2181-4562-2023-2>

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Саҳифаловчи/Page Maker/Верстка: Абдураҳмон Хасанов

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МАДАНИЯТ ВА САҢЪАТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ КУЛЬТУРА И ИСКУССТВО | JOURNAL OF CULTURE AND ART

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KAMARA KAMALOVA'S DIRECTING METHODOLOGY AS A BRIGHT EXAMPLE OF AUTHOR'S THEORY IN UZBEK CINEMATOGRAPHY

ANNOTATION

This scientific article provides information about the life and creative activity of Kamara Kamalova, who created more than a dozen feature, animated and documentary films in the history of Uzbek cinema. Almost every film by Kamalova was marked by international festivals. The article analyzes and describes the director's filmography, as well as comparison and continuity of the author's theory.

Key words: auteur cinema, film theory, director, genre, director's personality, children's cinema, script, film festival.

QAMARA KAMOLOVANING REJISSYORLIK USLUBIYOTI, O'ZBEK KINOSINING MUALLIF NAZARIYASI YORQIN NAMUNASI SIFATIDA

АННОТАЦИЯ

Mazkur ilmiy maqolada o'zbek kinosi tarixida o'ndan ortiq badiiy, animatsion va hujjatli filmlar yaratgan Qamara Kamolovanning hayoti va ijodiy faoliyati haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan. Kamolovanning deyarli har bir filmi xalqaro festivallarda nishonlangan. Maqolada rejissyorning filmografiyasi, shuningdek, muallif nazariyasining qiyoslanishi va uzluksizligi tahlil qilinadi va tavsiflanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: muallif kinosi, kino nazariyasi, rejissyor, janr, rejissyor shaxsiyati, bolalar kinosi, ssenariy, kinofestival.

РЕЖИССЕРСКАЯ МЕТОДОЛОГИЯ КАМАРЫ КАМАЛОВОЙ КАК ЯРКИЙ ПРИМЕР АВТОРСКОЙ ТЕОРИИ В УЗБЕКСКОМ КИНО

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье представлена информация о жизни и творческой деятельности Камары Камаловой – создавшей в истории узбекского кинематографа свыше десятка игровых, мультипликационных и документальных фильмов. Почти каждый фильм Камаловой был отмечен международными фестивалями. В статье проводится анализ и описание фильмографии режиссера, а также сопоставление и преемственность авторской теории.

Ключевые слова: авторское кино, кино теория, режиссёр, жанр, личность режиссера, детское кино, сценарий, кинофестиваль.

Before the emergence of the author's theory, the film was perceived as a product of the film industry - the combined work of the director, screenwriter, composer and actors. What the Cahiers du cinema theorists have noticed, however, is that even within Hollywood's assembly line studio system, bright individuals, authentic authors such as Alfred Hitchcock [1] and John Ford (as well as Fritz Lang and Orson Welles) have successfully worked. In film criticism, they were nicknamed "Hitchcock-Hawkins" (after Hitchcock and Hawkes), and their theory was called *politiques des auteurs* - the strategy or politics of authorship [2].

Theorists of auteur cinema for the first time reasonably formulated that the director is a key figure in the entire film process and the author (French *auteur*) of a film (considered as a work of art) [3].

Such a judgment confirms the individual film language inherent in each director: Despite the fact that a whole team is working on the film, adherents of auteur cinema have seen that all the activities of this team (the film crew) are aimed only at the most adequate transfer of the director's artistic intention, as in a picture of an artist or a writer's novel. Without the intention of the director, the activities of the collective (crew) are meaningless. The author's theory is associated with the French New Wave. At the present moment, the existence of auteur cinema is not in doubt either among the audience or critics. Films are recognized as "author's" in which there is an individual look (handwriting) of the author [4].

Kamara Kamalova. Photo from private archive.

The film director's profession is multifaceted and responsible, requiring specific managerial qualities. Moreover, this profession, is contraindicated for a woman. Kamara Kamalova is a unique example of this kind. She is one of the few representatives of the "female gender" who dared to turn to the most difficult activity of a film director. I wouldn't be mistaken to call her most hardworking and giving birth to stars (her movies gave a greenlight for a great number of local celebrities) Uzbek female director – She's just the only one in Uzbek film history with such successful career that lasts over half century.

She has an ordinary biography. Born in Tashkent in 1938. Finished school. She studied at VGIK in the workshop of Grigory Roshal. Then she appeared at the Uzbek film studio in the mid-60s. After this she immediately plunged into the atmosphere of collective creativity, friendly discussions. As a diploma work with other classmates, she staged a short film "Good afternoon". After graduating from university, Kamalova did not see debut opportunities in big film production so she went into animation and TV. Almost ten years of activity in animation helped Kamara to gain experience, to form her own unique direct naive style, which was reborn into a meaningful directorial style in the process of film production, to become a real author. The main genre direction of Kamalova's work is the youth theme, the problem of generations. She is fascinated by plots of romance, betrayal, reassessment of values dedicated to love, the confrontation of sincere feelings with meanness, kindness and cruelty.

She is committed to children's topics, which she talks about in her first full-length feature film, "Bitter Berry" (1975). And the stylistic orientation of the work is the same as in her best animated films. Two girls Lali and Nargiz live in the workers' settlement. Nargiz is older than her girlfriend, the world of her hobbies is not aligned with Lali experiences, who is at that innocent age when you still don't think about the complexity of the world. During the holidays, girls spend a lot of time in the garden and in nature, getting to know their peers along the way. One of them is the boy Erkin, already at a young age not devoid of the punk bully moods. Erkin does not really think about his actions. He is far from being able to appreciate the sincerity of Nargiz, who told him about the red bird that lives in the rocks ... In order to assert himself in the eyes of the guys, he climbs the rocks and destroys the bird's nest. Heartbroken bird throwing herself from a height, breaks right in front of the guys ... So the parable comes into contact with reality, goodness turns into hatred and misfortune.

The work of Kamalova conquered everyone with the integrity of the artistic embodiment of the poetic theme. Picturesque landscapes, plasticity and dynamism with which little actors reveal the philosophical essence of the events taking place on the screen are captured from the first frame. The death of a red bird is interpreted by the author not just as an act of heartlessness, senseless cruelty, but as a warning, as a call for sensitivity, goodness between people. Appeal to all the best and quivering in a person, his soul. The film brought wide popularity to the director, received a special diploma from the jury of the competition for children at the Moscow International Film Festival.

Great success always pleases, but it also imposes a huge responsibility. A problem arises before the creator of the film - how to make sure that the result achieved is not accidental, to back it up with a new achievement, preferably even more impressive.

"Someone else's happiness" (1978) - The director encountered an extraordinary attempt to present on the screen a complex human character in Mar Baidzhiev's script "Someone else's happiness". Once upon a time there was a collective farm chairman. Picky and strict, haunting neither himself nor others. By external standards, he was a good leader, his household did not limp, carried out the plan, he ruled with an iron fist for many years, until the time came for a well-deserved rest. But why is he so restless? What makes Abdurakhman, an elderly man, again and again return to the past days, sort out in his memory the echoes of previous, almost forgotten events?

These doubts are justified: from a distance of time, Abdurakhman-aka sees that much of what he did cannot be called fair. More than once, for the sake of a "just" cause, he offended people, did not take into account their will, forcibly imposed his decisions ... and nothing could be returned ...

In the film "Will you go out tomorrow?" (1980) according to the script by K. Lozinsky, director Kamalova creates a surprisingly subtle, full of sunny kindness and cunning film narration, in which many wonderful qualities of a children's artist, endowed with a special talent for "deep vision", the ability to very easily in the form of a game, conduct a confidential and serious conversation with the child ... The entire film "Will you go out tomorrow?" illuminated by a kind smile, not laughter, but a smile, sometimes ironic, but more often sly and insightful. In the film, we are not driven by the plot, but by the excitement of the observer, the researcher of human characters. Behind each character by the end of the tape grows the silhouette of a future adult.

In the courtyard of the new Tashkent house, the guys are playing their multi-day game "Moydodyr". Who does not know which of them has not read this, the classic work of Korney Chukovsky. The distribution of roles, the production of costumes, and the game itself become, as it were, a background against which very difficult relationships between the guys unfold. Here are accurately captured character traits, actions, expressions borrowed from adults, ruthlessly characterizing this or that social environment in which the child grows up. Here is the awakening of the first feelings, and the first steps towards asserting one's personality, one's independence, or vice versa, the ability to adapt to circumstances. Here and courageous dedication, the ability to give up a cherished desire in favor of another. In a word, in all this children's game, numerous nuances of human relationships are clearly manifested. This film is certainly interesting for adults as well.

The film "Our grandson works in the police" (1983) was an attempt to draw a fluent and lively, unadorned portrait of a young contemporary, to show the relationship between the older and younger generations.. What should a young police officer do if the detained thief-convict turned out to be his classmate! Probably, as in other cases, to actively intervene in the fate of a stumbled person. Do not be indifferent, try to revive in him faith in a good human beginning ... And what about a drunken brawler, if his wife, who is expecting a child, tearfully begs not to take her husband to the police! To take pity on a woman, to confine himself to a stern warning to a bully ... In doing so, Elyar Nigmatov is guided by his own ideas about goodness and decency. He is used to trusting people. But it turns out that his noble deeds or intentions do not always lead to the desired results, sometimes even have tragic consequences. In his former classmate Pulatov, Elyar does not immediately recognize the killer who covers his tracks, he confesses only to the fact of a "small" theft. At the hands of a forgiven drunkard-debaucher, his best friend and fellow student perishes. Elyar experiences his death especially painfully, because regardless of the objective circumstances, he considers himself the culprit of what happened.

The mistakes that the hero of the film goes through are not inherent to him alone. But Elyar is a man of duty and conscience, and this is precisely what indicates that he did not get into the police by chance. Elyar is deeply worried about the unwillingness of his grandfather and grandmother, who raised him, to understand the seriousness of his attitude to his chosen profession. Old people believe that with a diploma from a law school, their grandson could get a quieter job. But the young man is adamant in his decision, although he will have to go through many bitter minutes before he is finally convinced that work in the police is his vocation. Mistakes coming from naivety and inexperience will remain in the past with time. Our hero is young and, of course, love will not bypass him. An accidental acquaintance with the nurse Gulya will leave a deep mark on his heart. Elyar learns that Gulya lives alone with her son, that her personal life has developed unsuccessfully. He will fall in love with a serious, reserved and even a little harsh young woman. But Elyar will need a lot of patience and kindness before Gulya opens her heart to him...

The film "About what didn't happen" (1985). The idea of creating a film came from Kamara after reading two stories by Tokareva "Centering" and "A Star in the Fog". How to retell the plot of the movie? This is just a joke episode in the life of a business woman, and yet, this episode allows the director to turn around in the elements of the funny, bizarre, excess in the context of everyday life, makes it possible to present the heroine to the viewer in her unconditional charm and waywardness., makes it possible to speculate and reflect on life cordially, with good irony. The heroine of the film is Aziza, Doctor of Biological Sciences. The problem of her scientific research is the isolation of the molecule of joy, the ultimate goal is to make all of humanity happy. But this is not a fantastic film, this is just some convention associated with the idea of the entire film narrative. Aziza is also pretty. Her old school friend recalls with admiration: "You were so beautiful that no one thought you were also smart." Aziza's family relations also developed well. The husband treats Aziza's scientific work with great interest and respect, tries to create all the conditions for her creative pursuits, to free her from household chores. And although he himself is a major builder, he always has time to raise their daughter and a gentle attentive attitude towards his wife.

The picture is close to idyllic, you say. But one day, when Aziza's husband, Timur, went on a business trip, by chance, in between times, a neighbor, a department store saleswoman, ran in to her, offered scarce fabric, and at the same time said that Timur had not gone anywhere, but lives on a neighboring street with a young unmarried secretary from the research institute, the same one where Aziza works. The news is stunning! And it's hard to believe and it's impossible to live in peace. Aziza involuntarily succumbs to the first impulse and, on the advice of a neighbor, tries to see for herself the insidious betrayal. At night, she climbs onto the roof of someone else's house to look into the secretary's window ... This is where a series of episodes begins, in which you will not immediately figure out where the real events are, where the imaginary actions are merciless revenge on the seducer and unfaithful husband. Life and fiction are miraculously reconciled in film narration. The spectator accepts the conditions of the given game and willingly joins it.

In this parallel duality of the film narrative, the personalities of the authors of the film, Tokareva and Kamalova, are strikingly revealed. Such pronounced individualities, such dissimilar characters, that it would seem impossible to imagine their creative symbiosis.

However, it took place and gave an interesting result. They were united by many years of reflection on women's destinies, their own many years of life experience, Kamara's confidence that every woman deserves happiness, and Victoria Tokareva's conviction that happiness is the work of the man himself was briefly and confidently expressed. from the lips of one of the characters in the film: "Love is work."

The film "Savage" (1988) is based on the story of the writer Rustam Ibragimbekov "Revenge". In it, as always in the works of this writer, we are talking about the formation of an extraordinary, active, impulsive person. Kamalova in the film is interested in the fate of the hero, his actions, seemingly dictated by the best of intentions, and unfair heavy retribution, which makes one recall the bitter proverb "No good deed goes unpunished". The action takes place in the 1950s in one of the densely populated Bukhara communal yards. Its inhabitants are people, many of whom were evacuated here during the war from different cities of the country. And among them is the hero of the picture, eighteen-year-old Alik, who grew up in this yard.

Kind and sympathetic, he is always ready to help, does not save in the face of arrogance, will engage in combat with brute force. And he will pay for his uncompromising attitude with several years that he will spend in prison. Upon his return, he will not find his beloved girl - she, having married, will leave for another city. Alik will see at the threshold of her apartment only the skin of a white lamb that he once presented, now turned into a doormat. And all the neighbors and sister, for whom he then stood up, will be at the wedding of the guy, his offender. Alik, having come to the wedding, stands and watches how fun and good everyone is without him. Yes, his act did not change anything and was in vain. The theme raised in the film "The Savage" is always modern.

The film "Everything around was covered with snow" (1995) is a lyrical story about the first love of a teenage girl. Quietly, measuredly flows life in a small village. But there are also dramas. Asal lost her mother. The culprits of the tragic death of a woman are predators who destroyed a herd of young gazelles, which she raised and fed. The inhabitants of the village exterminated a pack of feral dogs. But one remained. The girl withdrew into herself, embittered at the whole wide world. And only the arrival of the huntsman Kamil in the reserve, communication with a new person, the confidence that arose in him melted the ice of loneliness in her soul.

The actors play without stormy scenes, only giving hints about the awakening feeling, or rather, its premonition, warmed by children's imagination and the dream of a wonderful friend, of a beautiful life in a distant city. The purity of the relationship determined the light, slightly sad tone of this lyrical film story. And it was filmed in such a coloristic manner, which surprisingly harmonizes with the nature of the reserve. The action takes place in late autumn, when the lush colors of summer are replaced by a light, lilac-golden gamut of withering.

The film "Road Under Heaven" (2005) is a kind of unique example of art-house ethno-symbolism. A girl named Muhabbat lives in a small village. She lives with a blind father. Her mother died several years ago. The older sister lives separately with her family, sometimes visiting her father's house. Muhabbat loves classmate Aziz. He seduces her.

They meet in secret. They think that their love will be eternal. One evening, Muhabbat confesses to Aziz that they can no longer hide their love, they need to get married soon. Learning that she should become a mother, he gets scared, quickly turns away and runs away. She understands that this is the end of their love. Sister Muhabbat is trying to sort things out. Comes to Aziz's mother. But Aziz's mother drives her away. The villagers gossip: some sympathize with her, others condemn her. At this time, Aziz's uncle arranges a big "kokil tui" for the long-awaited son, and Aziz's family celebrates this event. At the same time, they give up their unwanted child Muhabbat. Kokil is a bunch of hair that is left on the head of a child. When the child is 5-6 years old, the parents with the child visit the holy place, cut off this bundle of hair and leave it there. Therefore, a holiday is established on the occasion. And this holiday is called "kokil tui". Those who do not have children, but wish to have a child, take away the left "kokil". Some people have children because of this ceremony. Another character Meliboy lived without a family. The wife left him. Meliboi's longing for the child was so strong that he decided to marry Mukhabbat. At the insistence of her relatives, Muhabbat agrees to marry a man who is not to her liking. Meliboy is happy. Finally, God sent a woman in whose womb is his hope. Meliboy is kind, soft, gentle and affectionate with Muhabbat. And Mukhabat gradually develops sympathy for him. She believed him, was able to appreciate the nobility of his soul. In the same village lives a strange woman - Oikizmo. It is, as it were, the conscience of this village, like a mirror in which everyone sees himself. The film uses ancient folk songs, rituals. The song "Yul Bulsin" runs throughout the film as a leitmotif, which sounds in five or six versions: nai sings with some sadness, the rubab cheers up, and the vocal part of the song becomes one of the heroes of the film. The film won the jury prize for the best director's work in Almaty at the EURASIA IFF.

"Don't forget me" (2013) is another children's film in Kamalova's filmography, as an ode to the debut "Bitter Berry" clearly echoes her both in plot and in compositional decisions. The plot of the film is simple at first glance: the girl Gulnoz spends the summer with her grandmother in the village, meets a neighbor girl, her peer Dilbar. Here, in the village, the father of Batyr, a friend of Gulnoz, keeps an apiary. Children spend time together, swim, though furtively from adults, in the lake. Having received a rabbit as a gift, they themselves decide to let the animals go: they run with them into the forest and release them in a clearing at the very edge of the forest. And then they observe the consequences of their good deed: at first, the rabbits sat down on their paws, hiding in the grass and not understanding what these children wanted from them, then, as if beside themselves with happiness, rushed into the forest, accompanied by the joyful laughter of children. There seems to be no action: here Gulnoz has found a beautiful butterfly and is carefully trying to stir it up so that it, flapping its wings, will fly away to another flower. But this does not happen, because the butterfly is dead, and Halima's grandmother says: "Everything has its beginning and its end".

The girl brought milk to grandfather Yarash. He picks apples for his children in his garden. And then he dies before little girl's eyes - life is so fragile. This is how the first collision of the girl with reality takes place: there is life and there is death, and the line between them is thin. This truth has already been known by her friend Dilbar, who is hiding in her world with dolls in a hut left to her, as if by memory, by her untimely deceased father. From here, she jealously watches the new man who has appeared with her mother, tearing off resentment and anger on the dolls. Unable to change anything, she runs away from home when she finds out that her mother has married this man. Childishly uncompromising, she flatly refuses to leave her grandmother, the house where her father's portrait hangs, and move to an unfamiliar city, to strangers.

The summer, filled with new impressions, new relationships, the first sorrows and disappointments, is passing. Her father comes for Gulnoz. Seeing her and her son off, Halima gives her granddaughter an album as a keepsake, which opens with her husband's pics. Children face the same issues as adults. But life consists of these feelings, experiences, they form the character, the personality of young heroes. "Kamalova, the director, is saved from melodramatic notes by a surprisingly accurate possession of everyday details, which makes her poetically colored tapes life-like. And this ability to create intricate subtle cinematography, while maintaining the authenticity of what is happening, is the talent of the director, who makes her work art, in contrast to non-art - a handicraft fake, wrote critic Elena Chaika [5].

And in fact, this is the most "intricate subtle cinematography" the ability to tell about what is happening in the child's soul, and keep the viewer's attention.

The well-known American film historian Andrew Sarris in "Notes on the Author's Theory" in 1962 describes the main features of the author's cinema.

1. Technical competence of the director as a criterion of value. A bad director is not always defined by a bad film. If the director has no technical competence and even elementary taste, then he falls out of the pantheon of directors.

2. The distinctive personality of the director as a criterion of value. The director in the group of his films must form a certain style, which will later become the criterion by which he will stand out as the author of specific works among many others. The manner of reflecting the reality of the film should correspond to the worldview of the director of this picture. Artistic reflection of a special worldview and forms the style of the author.

3. The director's vision is still very ambiguous, as part of it cannot be expressed in non-cinematic terms and is implanted in this specific imagery. Sarris himself calls this "inner meaning" the soul. The soul, on the other hand, is defined by the critic as the minimal and barely perceptible difference between two persons, provided that other things are equal.

Summing up all these features that Sarris figured out according to Cahiers du cinema ideas and Kamara Kamalova's directing experience and filmography we can definitely assert her involvement to the Author Theory's and Cinema, because she has her own certain style, in many cases she wrote scripts herself or edited them, and always knew what kind of movie she wants to create and for whom. Because the most important thing for the creator to find your own specific theme. Kamalova's films are unhurried, kind, poetic, they have few dramatic plot twists and turns, but many picturesque plans, the unity of man with living creatures, with nature. The action takes place in picturesque villages, mountains, fields, in orchards, vegetable gardens, near streams. They are best for young viewer as eye rest and lessons of kindness, innocent relationships, friendship and love.

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ISSN: 2181-4562
DOI Journal 10.56017/2181-4562

МАДАНИЯТ ВА САНЪАТ ЖУРНАЛИ

I-ЖИЛД, 2-СОН

ЖУРНАЛ КУЛЬТУРА И ИСКУССТВО

ТОМ-I, НОМЕР-2

JOURNAL OF CULTURE AND ART

VOLUME-I, ISSUE-2

2023 йил 31 март куни чоп этилди.

«Маданият ва санъат» электрон журнали 2023 йил 24 февраль куни № 065356-сонли гувоҳнома билан оммавий ахборот воситаси сифатида давлат рўйхатидан ўтказилган.

Муассис: «IMFAKTOR Pages» масъулияти чекланган жамияти.

Таҳририят манзили: 100152, Тошкент шаҳри, Учтепа тумани, “Ватан” МФЙ, Чилонзор 24-мавзеси, 2-уй.

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